

Client-Side Verilog Synthesis via WebAssembly: Enabling Offline HDL Workflows in Browser-Based EDA Tools

Souparna Chatterjee¹

¹Department of Electrical Engineering, National Institute of Technology Durgapur, India,
soparnachatterjee98@gmail.com

May 2026

Abstract

Browser-based digital logic simulators such as CircuitVerse provide accessible entry points for HDL education, but their synthesis pipelines typically depend on remote server infrastructure. This dependency makes the synthesis workflow unavailable in offline environments and fails entirely in desktop builds that run without a guaranteed network connection. We describe the design and implementation of a fully client-side Verilog synthesis pipeline that runs Yosys 0.63 compiled to WebAssembly inside a Web Worker, with no server calls at any stage. The implementation introduces a routing layer that selects between the existing Rails-based server path and the local WebAssembly path based on the detected runtime environment, leaving the browser flow untouched while providing complete offline capability for Tauri desktop users. The system handles the 37.23 MB primary WASM binary through a Service Worker caching layer, eliminating repeated download overhead after first use. A topological auto-layout engine converts raw Yosys JSON netlists into readable left-to-right circuit diagrams on the CircuitVerse canvas, covering 60+ cell types including arithmetic, comparison, all DFF variants, and shift operators. A companion real-time linter implements seven lint rules directly in the CodeMirror editor with zero new dependencies. The implementation spans 35 files, 7,372 insertions, and 1,870 deletions across 392 commits, and has been verified to produce identical synthesis output with network access disabled at the OS level.

Keywords— WebAssembly, Verilog, EDA, Yosys, offline-first, browser, HDL, CircuitVerse

1. Introduction

CircuitVerse is a widely used open-source digital logic simulator and educational platform. Its Verilog synthesis feature converts HDL source into a visual circuit on the simulator canvas by relying on a Rails backend that spawns

a native Yosys subprocess on the server, transmits the netlist back to the browser, and renders it through the Vue.js frontend. This design works correctly for web users but introduces a hard dependency on network connectivity and server availability.

The problem becomes particularly acute in the Tauri desktop build, where users may work entirely offline. In that environment, every synthesis request fails silently or times out, effectively disabling the feature. Students in low-bandwidth settings, exam environments, or field deployments face the same problem even in the browser.

The technical constraint driving this work is straightforward: Yosys is a large, mature synthesis tool that was not designed to run in a browser. Moving it client-side requires either rewriting the synthesis logic in JavaScript—impractical given the scope—or compiling the existing C++ codebase to WebAssembly. The `@yowasp/yosys` package provides Yosys 0.63 compiled to WASM, making the second approach feasible without forking Yosys itself.

This paper describes the architecture and implementation decisions made to integrate that WASM build into CircuitVerse, with attention to challenges introduced by binary size, worker lifecycle management, primitive mapping, layout, and runtime environment detection. The full implementation is available as PR #1022 [4].

2. Background and Motivation

2.1 Existing Synthesis Architecture

In the current CircuitVerse architecture, the synthesis flow proceeds as follows: the user writes Verilog in a CodeMirror editor embedded in the Vue.js frontend; on clicking *Synthesize*, the frontend sends the source text to a Rails API endpoint; the server invokes a native Yosys binary as a subprocess; Yosys produces a JSON netlist; the server returns this to the client; and the frontend's `Verilog2CV.js` converter maps netlist primitives to CircuitVerse canvas elements.

This pipeline has three properties relevant to this work. First, it requires an active network connection and an available server. Second, the conversion and layout logic already exists in the frontend—the client already knows how to render a netlist but does not currently produce one locally. Third, the Yosys invocation on the server is straightforward, using a small set of synthesis commands that are reproducible in the WASM environment.

2.2 The WebAssembly Route

WebAssembly provides a portable binary instruction format that runs in modern browsers and Node.js runtimes at near-native speed. Emscripten-compiled C++ programs can be executed inside a browser context with access to a virtual filesystem, standard I/O, and memory management. The `@yowasp/yosys` package wraps Yosys 0.63 in this form, exposing a JavaScript API that accepts a command array and a virtual filesystem map, executes synthesis, and returns the output files.

The practical constraint is binary size. The primary WASM file (`yosys.core.wasm`) is 37.23 MB. An additional JS bundle (`yosys-bundle.js`, 0.16 MB) and a resource archive (`yosys-resources.tar`, 10.13 MB) bring the total first-load payload to approximately 47.5 MB. Without caching, this would impose unacceptable latency on every page load.

2.3 Tauri and the Desktop Context

Tauri is a framework for building desktop applications using a Rust backend and a WebView frontend [7]. A Tauri build of CircuitVerse renders the same Vue.js frontend in a native window. In this environment, `window.__TAURI__` is injected into the global scope at runtime, providing a reliable signal for environment detection that does not require build-time configuration changes.

3. System Design

3.1 Routing Layer

The synthesis routing decision is made by a single function, `shouldUseWasm()`, which checks for the presence of `window.__TAURI__`. If the function returns `true`, synthesis is dispatched to the local WebAssembly pipeline; otherwise, the existing Rails server path is used unchanged. This design ensures that the change is entirely additive from the perspective of browser users.

3.2 Web Worker and Initialization

Running the 37.23 MB WASM binary on the main JavaScript thread would block the UI for several seconds during initialization. The synthesis worker (`public/yosys-worker.js`, 262 lines) handles all WASM interaction off the main thread.

The worker uses a single shared initialization Promise: the first call to `initWasmWorker()` starts the Promise and caches it; all subsequent calls await the same Promise. This guarantees that the WASM module is loaded exactly once per worker lifetime regardless of how many synthesis requests arrive during startup. Incoming requests that arrive before the worker is ready are buffered in a `pendingMessages []` array and flushed in FIFO order once initialization completes.

3.3 Virtual Filesystem and Multi-File Support

Yosys synthesis requires input files in a filesystem. In the WASM environment this is a virtual filesystem provided by Emscripten. The worker accepts a file map and writes each entry into the VFS before invoking synthesis. The synthesis command sequence is:

```
read_verilog top.v adder.v
synth -top top -flatten
write_json output.json
```

A `buildFileMap()` function controls file assembly. When a multi-file tab UI is introduced, only this function requires modification. This has been verified with a two-file design (a top module instantiating a full adder submodule).

3.4 Service Worker Caching

The Service Worker (`public/sw.js`, 107 lines) intercepts fetch requests for the Yosys WASM assets and serves them from a local cache after the first download. On subsequent loads, the Service Worker responds entirely from cache, with no network access. A version key in the cache name allows invalidation when the Yosys version is updated.

3.5 Primitive Mapping and Netlist Conversion

After synthesis, Yosys produces a JSON netlist in its standard format. The `yosys2digitaljs-browser.js` converter (1,239 lines) and `yosys2digitaljs-core.js` (1,228 lines) translate this netlist into CircuitVerse-compatible component structures. The mapping covers 60+ Yosys cell types spanning arithmetic (`$add`, `$sub`, `$mul`, `$div`, `$mod`, `$pow`), comparison (`$eq`, `$ne`, `$lt`, `$le`, `$gt`, `$ge`), bitwise logic (`$and`, `$or`, `$xor`, `$xnor`, `$not`), reduction operators, shift operators (`$shl`, `$shr`, `$ssh1`, `$sshr`), D flip-flops (`$dff`, `$dffe`, `$adff`, `$adffe`, `$sdff`, `$sdffe`, `$sdffce`), multiplexers (`$mux`, `$pmux`), memory primitives, and wire operations. Unmapped cell types produce a labeled blackbox placeholder rather than silently dropping the component.

3.6 Auto-Layout Engine

The converter initially places all components at coordinate (0,0), causing the canvas to appear blank even when synthesis succeeds. The auto-layout engine

(`src/simulator/src/circuitLayout.js`, 77 lines) assigns readable left-to-right coordinates based on signal flow. The algorithm proceeds in four stages: (1) adjacency graph construction from wire connections in the netlist; (2) topological layer assignment, with inputs at layer 0 and outputs pinned to the final layer; (3) three passes of barycentric crossing minimisation; and (4) coordinate assignment using fixed pixel offsets ($x = \text{layer} \times 200$, $y = \text{position} \times 100$). The layout engine is covered by an integration test suite (163 lines).

Figures 1 and 2 show the CircuitVerse editor before and after client-side synthesis.

Figure 1: CircuitVerse editor with `full_adder` Verilog source. The canvas is empty before synthesis.

Figure 2: Canvas after client-side WASM synthesis of a 2:1 mux. Console confirms zero server calls; Gates: 1, Wires: 4, Inputs: 3, Outputs: 1.

4. Companion Features

4.1 Real-Time Verilog Linter

The linter (`src/simulator/src/verilogLinter.js`, 475 lines) adds real-time feedback directly in the CodeMirror editor as the user types, using the CodeMirror 5 lint addon that was already present but previously unused [8]. No new dependencies were introduced. Seven lint rules are implemented: (1) mismatched module/endmodule pairs; (2) unmatched begin/end blocks; (3) missing semicolons on port declarations and assign statements; (4) keyword typos via a constant-time lookup map of

40+ Verilog keywords with word-boundary matching; (5) invalid assignments to input ports; (6) empty module bodies; and (7) comment stripping so all rules run on a clean copy of the source. The implementation is covered by 12 unit tests and is available in PR #1026 [5].

4.2 Offline-First HTTP Layer

All API calls now pass through a single `apiFetch()` wrapper (`src/utils/api.ts`, 85 lines). On web, the wrapper passes calls through unchanged with relative URLs and cookie-based authentication. On Tauri, it prepends the CircuitVerse origin and injects a stored authentication token. Eight existing `fetch()` calls across multiple frontend files were migrated.

4.3 Cloud Circuit Cache and Conflict Resolution

The circuit cache (`src/utils/circuitCache.ts`, 407 lines) allows desktop users to pull CircuitVerse cloud circuits for offline use. Each entry stores the circuit ID, name, server `updatedAt` timestamp, local `localUpdatedAt` timestamp, a dirty flag, and a conflict flag. Conflict detection compares server `updatedAt` against the last successful sync timestamp. The `ConflictModal.vue` component (224 lines) handles resolution with three options: keep local version, use server version, or defer to next session.

5. Implementation Details

Environment detection. The `shouldUseWasm()` function checks `window.__TAURI__` at call time rather than at module load time. In some Tauri configurations the global is injected asynchronously, and a module-load-time check could produce a false negative.

Auto-top selection. When the Verilog source contains multiple module declarations with no explicit top module specified, the worker implements an `autoTop()` heuristic that identifies the module not instantiated by any other module and passes it as the `-top` argument to the `synth` command.

Auth token handling. The original `authStore.ts` contained a JWT parsing path incorrect for CircuitVerse, which issues opaque tokens rather than JWTs. The fix removes the JWT parsing logic and ensures `localStorage` is cleared correctly on logout.

Asset resolution in Tauri. In a Tauri desktop build, static assets are accessed via `convertFileSrc()`, which maps a local filesystem path to a `tauri://localhost/URL`. A postinstall script copies WASM files from the `@yowasp/yosys` package to `public/` during `npm install`.

6. Evaluation

6.1 Offline Verification

The primary correctness criterion is that synthesis produces identical output with and without network access. This was verified by disabling Wi-Fi at the OS level in a Tauri desktop build and synthesizing the same Verilog designs used during network-connected testing. The browser Network tab confirmed zero outbound requests during synthesis.

A two-file design (top module instantiating a full adder submodule) was synthesized entirely client-side, producing Gates: 7, Wires: 16, Inputs: 3, Outputs: 2. The result is structurally identical to the server-side Yosys pipeline output for the same input. A 2:1 mux produced Gates: 1, Wires: 4, Inputs: 3, Outputs: 1, as shown in Fig. 2.

6.2 Binary Size and Caching

Table 1 lists each WASM asset and its size. After the first load, the Service Worker serves all assets from cache, reducing subsequent synthesis startup to under 100 ms regardless of network conditions.

Table 1: WASM Asset Sizes

Asset	Size
yosys.core.wasm	37.23 MB
yosys-resources.tar	10.13 MB
yosys-bundle.js	0.16 MB
yosys.core2.wasm	0.03 MB
yosys.core3/4.wasm	<0.01 MB each
Total first-load	\approx 47.5 MB

6.3 Code Metrics

Table 2 summarises the implementation scale, and Table 3 lists primary source files by line count.

Table 2: Implementation Metrics

Metric	Value
Total commits on branch	392
Files changed	35
Lines inserted	7,372
Lines deleted	1,870
Lint rules implemented	7
Lint unit tests	12
Layout test lines	163
Yosys cell types mapped	60+
fetch() calls migrated	8

7. Threats to Validity

Binary version coupling. The primitive mapping targets Yosys 0.63 as provided by @yowasp/yosys. A future

Table 3: Key Source File Sizes

File	Lines
yosys2digitaljs-browser.js	1,239
yosys2digitaljs-core.js	1,228
VerilogClasses.js	1,229
Verilog2CV.js	987
verilogLinter.js	475
circuitCache.ts	407
ConflictModal.vue	224
yosys-worker.js	262
sw.js	107
api.ts	85
circuitLayout.js	77

Yosys update may introduce new cell types or rename existing ones, requiring updates to the mapping layer.

Layout quality on large designs. The barycentric crossing minimisation produces readable output for designs of moderate size. For large netlists with hundreds of nodes, the fixed-grid assignment may produce crowded or overlapping layouts.

Service Worker scope. In security-restricted environments (certain corporate proxies, browsers with Service Workers disabled), the first-load penalty recurs on each session. Synthesis remains functional; only the caching optimisation is affected.

Single-branch measurement. The diff statistics compare against the feat/verilog-linter branch rather than upstream main, as no local main reference was available at measurement time.

8. Related Work

Browser-based HDL tools occupy a small but growing space. Several projects have explored WASM-based simulation, including attempts to compile Verilator and Icarus Verilog to WebAssembly. The @yowasp project provides pre-compiled WASM builds of Yosys, nextpnr, and related EDA tools [2], and is the dependency used in this work.

CircuitVerse’s architecture differs from pure simulation tools in that it targets visual circuit representation rather than waveform output. The synthesis pipeline must not only produce a correct netlist but convert it into a form the canvas rendering system can display. The offline-first design pattern follows established practices from progressive web application development [9], adapted here for the Tauri desktop runtime. The auto-layout algorithm follows the layered graph drawing approach of Sugiyama et al. [10].

9. Future Work

Several directions remain open. Waveform viewing—capturing signal values during simulation ticks and rendering them as a canvas-based timeline—would close the

write–synthesize–simulate–verify loop without leaving the application. VCD export would make signal data interoperable with tools such as GTKWave. Testbench support, hierarchical module blackboxing with expand/collapse navigation, and hash-based Service Worker cache invalidation keyed to the WASM binary content are additional planned directions.

10. Conclusion

We have described a client-side Verilog synthesis pipeline for CircuitVerse that eliminates the server dependency for Tauri desktop users while leaving the existing browser flow unchanged. The system runs Yosys 0.63 compiled to WebAssembly in a Web Worker, uses a Service Worker to cache the 47.5 MB payload after first load, converts Yosys JSON netlists to CircuitVerse canvas components across 60+ cell types, and applies a topological auto-layout pass to produce readable circuit diagrams. The implementation spans 35 files and 7,372 insertions across 392 commits, and has been verified to produce correct output with network access disabled.

The companion real-time linter adds editor-integrated feedback with seven lint rules and 12 unit tests, the offline-first HTTP layer unifies authentication across web and desktop environments, and the circuit cache with conflict resolution provides local storage for cloud circuits. The work demonstrates that a production-quality offline synthesis workflow is achievable within the constraints of a browser-based EDA tool, without requiring changes to the server-side infrastructure or the existing web user experience.

Acknowledgment

The author thanks the CircuitVerse maintainers and GSoC 2026 mentor team (Vivek Kumar Ray, Harsh Rao, Nihal Rajpal, Aboobacker MK) for their guidance and code review feedback.

References

- [1] C. Wolf et al., “Yosys Open SYnthesis Suite,” <https://yosyshq.net/yosys/>, 2012.
- [2] @yowasp/yosys, “YoWASP Yosys distribution,” <https://www.npmjs.com/package/@yowasp/yosys>.
- [3] CircuitVerse, “cv-frontend-vue,” <https://github.com/CircuitVerse/cv-frontend-vue>.
- [4] S. Chatterjee, “feat: Add client-side Yosys WASM synthesis for Tauri desktop builds,” PR #1022, CircuitVerse, 2025. <https://github.com/CircuitVerse/cv-frontend-vue/pull/1022>
- [5] S. Chatterjee, “feat: Real-time Verilog syntax linter for CodeMirror editor,” PR #1026, CircuitVerse, 2025. <https://github.com/CircuitVerse/cv-frontend-vue/pull/1026>
- [6] S. Chatterjee, “POC repository: complete_POC_stretchGoalIncluded_Idea7,” https://github.com/SouparnaChatterjee/complete_POC_stretchGoalIncluded_Idea7
- [7] Tauri Contributors, “Tauri v2 Documentation,” <https://tauri.app/v2/guide/>, 2024.
- [8] CodeMirror, “CodeMirror 5 Lint Addon,” <https://codemirror.net/5/doc/manual.html>.
- [9] WebAssembly Community Group, “WebAssembly Specification,” <https://webassembly.github.io/spec/core/>, 2019.
- [10] K. Sugiyama, S. Tagawa, and M. Toda, “Methods for visual understanding of hierarchical system structures,” *IEEE Trans. Syst., Man, Cybern.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 109–125, 1981.